

METHODOLOGY OF POPULARIZATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCES IN FINE ARTS

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Annotation. Currently, there are various opinions, views, and approaches to teaching based on advanced pedagogical technologies. This is not accidental, of course. The constant search for establishing teaching based on modern, advanced pedagogical technologies, creating understandable and interesting areas of the educational process for students remains an important task of the teacher. This article discusses what a teacher should follow when designing lessons on pedagogical technology, and the existence of three main approaches to advanced pedagogical experience.

Keywords: technology, teacher, education, experience, lesson, project, instruction, methods, educational process, upbringing.

Introduction. One of the main factors of the development processes taking place in the world is related to the training of highly competent specialists in each field. As the initial basis of competencies, educational competencies are recognized, first of all[1]. One of the urgent problems of Uzbek pedagogical science is the formation and development of national and world cultural values of young people, in particular, the formation and development of educational competencies in artistic and visual activities, which are among the issues of great relevance today.

A number of scientific researches are being conducted worldwide to develop a didactic system for the formation of basic, meta-subject, artistic and aesthetic, and general cultural competencies of students in visual arts classes, and to improve the methodological foundations of teaching visual arts using interactive software tools.[2] Especially in the process of teaching art subjects, the cultivation of visual literacy, the use of drawing and pictorial models in design and media arts, information and communication technologies, the development of critical, creative thinking, ethical skills, personal and social, intercultural competence in students are of particular importance.[3] At the same time, the development of life skills through the use of art-media tools and technologies in fine arts lessons, the formation of patriotic and civic

competencies in students on the basis of art education require the implementation of creative activities based on prioritizing vitagen education.

Materials and methods. In today's new Uzbekistan, which is developing in step with the times, as one of the important areas of reforming the education system, in particular, the subject "Fine Arts" taught in general secondary schools, special attention is paid, first of all, to the formation of field-specific educational competencies in students.[4] Indeed, in our republic, the state social policy pays special attention to the interests of the individual and the priority of education, the rich national values, cultural and historical traditions and intellectual heritage of our people, and the upbringing of a creative generation with creative thinking is an important factor in the process of Uzbekistan's integration into the world community. These factors mean that the use of the educational and educational opportunities of fine arts is of great importance.[5]

The main feature of the traditional approach is that the teacher, while teaching the subject of fine arts, explains certain information while presenting it, and the student stores this knowledge in memory. In this case, the concept of "knowledge" is understood in the sense of information on educational materials stored in memory.[6] For example, the main task of composition is to develop creative artistic imagination in students, to visually perceive reality in life, to form artistic taste and culture, to acquire competencies related to creating compositions from visual activities, and to ensure the effective use of theoretical and practical knowledge gained from science in social life. This means that a systematic approach is necessary in the formation of field-specific academic competencies in students in visual arts classes.[7]

From the first days of Uzbekistan's independence, the main emphasis on the fundamental changes that are being implemented in all aspects of the life of society on its independent path of development has been to further strengthen the foundation of our national, educational traditions, and enrich them with modern advanced teaching methods of the world by harmonizing them with the requirements of the time. This, in turn, requires strengthening the material, technical and information base of the education system, providing the educational process with high-quality educational literature and advanced pedagogical technologies.

Therefore, the formation of professional skills of pedagogical personnel on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies in the process of training them is an important requirement of today. The technological approach to education is one of the tools that actively influences the pedagogical process and determines its effectiveness, integrity, and success. Theoretical and methodological analysis of the technological approach to

education shows that the social order of society is closely related to the requirements for the level of development of pedagogical science.

One of the important tasks of all parts of the education system, especially in the general secondary education system, which is its most important formative component, is to prepare students - young people for deep and solid knowledge in all areas of science, to prepare them for successful continuation of their studies at higher levels of education in the future and to become worthy personnel. To successfully implement this goal, it is necessary to continuously improve education, establish strong mutual relations between schools, academic lyceums, higher education, popularize innovations and best practices in the field of education, and consistently conduct methodological cooperation.

Discussion and results. Teacher training is important in designing training sessions on advanced pedagogical technologies. Observations and analyses show that teachers face serious difficulties in this activity, which requires them to have high qualifications and experience. Because it requires a more creative approach to create specific instructions. An experienced teacher determines which important points in the lesson should be remembered by the students, and which ones should be simply known.

The nature of the lesson depends on the creativity and skill of the teacher. The work on organizing and conducting lessons should consist mainly of two parts: preparing a lesson plan and implementing it. Preparing a lesson plan is a product of the teacher's creative activity and has a number of common features. The project is based on the activities that the teacher and students will carry out together in the future.

It begins with an analysis based on the requirements of state educational standards. The analysis focuses on how the elements of the content of the information (knowledge, skills and abilities, creative experience, relationships) are presented in the programs and reflected in textbooks. Then the content of the lesson topic is studied, the goal set for studying this or that topic, the didactic goal of education, the goals of the teacher and students, the implementation and assessment sheets of the goals, the amount of homework assigned, test questions on the topics, rating control steps, and the method of mastering at the standard level are determined in advance. Modern pedagogical technology requires creative activity for each of the stages, from clearly setting the goal of education to assessing its results. When designing lessons according to pedagogical technology, it is important for the teacher to adhere to the following: at the beginning of the lesson, arouse interest in the students in studying the topic being studied; announce the learning objectives of the lesson to them, make changes to them if necessary; alternate the lesson with forms of organizing educational activities;

developing critical thinking through reading and writing in lectures and practical sessions, using interactive methods selected for the topic, and others.

When designing a topic, the content of its name, the hours allocated to it, the goals of the teacher and the student, various forms of tasks, basic concepts, the style and form of the teacher's management of the educational activity of the student, graphic and technical means of teaching, diagnostic methods, etc. are indicated.

Pedagogical experience is determined by educators on the basis of the knowledge, qualifications, and skills acquired in the process of practical work and is interpreted as one of the main sources of pedagogical skill and development of pedagogical science. Experience that opens up new opportunities in the education of children and achieves creative results using new forms, methods, and methods in the formation of educational work can be called advanced work experience. There are about 40 concepts of "Advanced pedagogical experience" in the literature on pedagogy. All of these concepts are interpreted as a tool that directs the pedagogical process towards a goal and influences the achievement of high indicators. There are three main approaches to advanced pedagogical experience.

They are:

- Approaching the work experience of a teacher who shows good results as an example compared to the work of other teachers;

- Approaching the activities of teachers who can implement scientific research and experimental-testing work into life and achieve good results;

- Approaching creative teachers who create new, unique knowledge. Searching for, studying, generalizing, applying and popularizing advanced work experiences are all stages of the main work processes of a senior educator or head. These stages are as follows:

The first stage. At this stage, the pedagogical process is observed. During the observation period, the advanced work experiences of educators and the good work of individual teachers are identified.

The second stage. At this stage, it is necessary to summarize the accumulated experience. The senior educator helps the teacher analyze all the evidence and select the main from the secondary. In this, the theoretical substantiation of the experience is of great importance. The ability to correctly use logical methods helps to draw the right conclusions.

The third stage. At this stage, the best practices are implemented and popularized. A single preschool educational institution can search for, find, study, generalize and

popularize the best practices of its educators or apply the best practices of other educators to the life of this institution.

When choosing the best practices selected for use in practice, the following criteria should be given importance.

- Its relevance;
- Programmability;
- The creation of conditions for application;
- The experience leads to good results;
- The stability of the achieved result.

The idea of expanding and deepening the content of education and its structure, including not only knowledge, skills, qualifications, but also the experience of creative activity that forms a universal culture, and relationships with the environment is very important. Advanced pedagogical and social experiences are an important factor in the formation of pedagogical skills. The main aspect of new pedagogical technologies is the need to re-create school textbooks at a high level.

The creation of textbooks should be carried out based on many years of scientific, cultural, aesthetic, and spiritual experience. Pedagogical activity in the educational process is creative in nature by its own labor. It is known that creativity arises only when a person faces a problem. Teaching activity has such a feature.

The main essence of pedagogical creativity is clearly defined by the purpose and nature of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical activity is the process of solving countless pedagogical problems that are subordinate to the personality of a person, his worldview, beliefs, consciousness, and behavior. Creativity in the work of a teacher is expressed in the methods of solving these problems, in the ability to find ways to solve them.

The source of pedagogical creativity is advanced pedagogical experience. Advanced pedagogical experience is very rich in problem situations. By advanced pedagogical experience, we understand the teacher's creative approach to his pedagogical task, the search for new, modern, effective, most appropriate ways and means in the education of students. Advanced pedagogical experience is the form and methods of work, methods and tools, as well as innovative technologies used by the teacher. Advanced pedagogical experience leads to the study, the discovery of new pedagogical phenomena and laws based on it, the introduction of good, qualitative changes in the educational process, the management of students' cognitive activity, the solution of problems of modeling the educational process in a new form. A creative teacher must

not only successfully teach and educate; he must also have research skills and qualifications to analyze the work experience of advanced teachers.

An advanced teacher always strives to learn about innovations in the field of pedagogy, uses the experience of other teachers and tries to generalize his own personal experience. The current development of science and technology requires that the teacher be creative, be able to think freely about important problems of his subject, convey scientific achievements to students, and finally, teach students to think creatively and conduct research. Therefore, the teacher must, first of all, acquire research skills. During the course of conducting scientific research, the teacher collects the experiences of scientists, analyzes them, and draws conclusions based on them.

In the process of using scientific conclusions in his practical activities, he acquires very important qualities necessary for a modern teacher. Advanced teachers pay special attention to the choice of teaching methods.

Although there are more common aspects of frontal, differentiated and individual activities of students, their organization requires a unique creative approach from the teacher. If the entire class, group and individual are influenced by the same method, then both education and creative approach will fail. The teacher's reliance on advanced pedagogical experiences in the formation of pedagogical skills will lead to good results. One of the most important tasks of visual arts classes is to teach how to read works of applied decorative and architectural arts. Works of visual arts reflect a certain content, such as a fairy tale, story, epic. Works of visual arts have their own language. In particular, artists reveal the content of the work using expressive means such as lines, colors, dimensions, composition, proportion, rhythm, symmetry, form.

Fine arts education is not only important in shaping the aesthetic education of students, but also plays a significant role in moral education. It should be recognized that fine arts education is important in terms of its great power in forming students' national pride and honor, the ideology of national independence, patriotism and international education, and the ideas of friendship and mutual assistance.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be said that it is necessary to further improve the quality of education by applying advanced pedagogical experiences in education. Through this, we will develop the following characteristics of our youth: - forming knowledge, attitudes and skills; - creating a basis for young people to strive for the world arena and increasing their competitiveness as mature personnel; 80 - forming their creativity and critical thinking skills. It should also be said that the main and greatest task facing us today is to educate and educate a fully developed, well-rounded individual.

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